

CMRxRecon2026: Towards Clinical Adoption of Ultra-Fast 4D Flow MRI: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

CMRxRecon2026: Towards Clinical Adoption of Ultra-Fast 4D Flow MRI

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

CMRxRecon2026

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

Four-dimensional (4D) flow MR imaging is a cutting-edge technique for visualizing and quantifying cardiovascular hemodynamics, providing high-resolution spatiotemporal information on blood flow patterns. It allows for the assessment of critical hemodynamic parameters, such as flow velocity, flow rate, wall shear stress, and vorticity, providing critical insights for cardiovascular diagnosis, treatment evaluation, and hemodynamic research. MR 4D flow has broad potential applications, including assessing aortic stenosis, aneurysms, and ventricular function, as well as guiding surgical planning and monitoring postoperative recovery.

Currently, the clinical application of 4D flow MR is constrained by prolonged acquisition times and computational complexity. Without acceleration techniques, a full cardiac cycle typically requires 30~60 minutes to capture, making it impractical for routine clinical workflows. Even with existing acceleration methods, such as parallel imaging and compressed sensing, scan times are often reduced to 10~20 minutes—still longer than the clinically desired range of within 5 minutes.

Furthermore, reconstruction of undersampled 4D flow datasets remains highly computationally intensive. The large data volumes and high acceleration factors demand substantial resources, limiting the feasibility of routine clinical use, especially in hardware-constrained environments. Developing resource-efficient reconstruction methods is critical to overcome this barrier and enable broader clinical adoption of 4D flow technology.

In addition to these challenges, there remains a significant gap in large-scale, standardized public datasets and challenges focused on 4D flow reconstruction. To our knowledge, there is currently no open challenge relating to 4D flow imaging, as most existing 4D flow reconstruction studies primarily rely on in-house data from either healthy individuals or simulations. This limitation hinders the validation of algorithms in real-world clinical scenarios, particularly for cases with diverse and complex flow patterns. Establishing an open dataset with cases of different diseases, such as stenosis, regurgitation, aneurysms, and dissections, is critical for testing algorithm robustness and adaptability.

This challenge builds on the success of previous efforts (CMRxRecon2023, CMRxRecon2024, and CMRxRecon2025) in advancing multi-contrast cardiac imaging reconstruction. Unlike prior challenges that focused on conventional 2D and 3D cardiac imaging, the proposed challenge shifts its focus to the unique and complex domain of 4D flow imaging. With its inclusion of both 3D spatial and 1D temporal dimensions, 4D flow presents significantly higher data dimensionality and computational demands. Moreover, unlike conventional structural imaging, which primarily emphasizes magnitude accuracy, 4D flow critically depends on precise phase reconstruction for calculating blood velocities. The focus on both magnitude and phase reconstruction accuracy, combined with the greater acceleration potential of 4D flow, presents new opportunities and challenges for advancing cutting-edge reconstruction techniques.

The dataset will be collected from 2~3 clinical centers and will comprise more than 200 cases, including a diverse range of diseases, such as aortic stenosis, regurgitation, aneurysms, coarctation, and dissections. This diversity ensures the simulation of real-world scenarios for robust algorithm evaluation.

Participants of this challenge will need to address two key objectives:

1. Accurate reconstruction under ultra-high acceleration factors: Develop algorithms capable of restoring high-quality images (including magnitude and phase) from highly undersampled data while ensuring the reliability of hemodynamic parameters.
2. Fast and accurate reconstruction with limited computational resources: Develop resource-efficient solutions that enable rapid reconstruction in hardware-constrained environments, making the technology viable for real-world clinical practice.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

4D flow, MRI reconstruction, high acceleration, computational efficiency, hemodynamic

Year

2026

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

1. The first challenge on 4D flow imaging and hemodynamic quantification: This challenge focuses on the speed issues of 4D flow imaging, aiming to address the pain points for its widespread clinical application. Beyond traditional magnitude image reconstruction, this task places an emphasis on precise flow velocity/phase reconstruction accuracy, which is critical for calculating clinically relevant hemodynamic parameters.
2. Real-World and multi-center evaluations: Currently, no publicly available 4D flow datasets include patient cases, as most 4D flow reconstruction studies rely on data from healthy individuals or simulations. This challenge provides a unique dataset encompassing various aortic diseases such as stenosis, regurgitation, aneurysms, and dissections. These real-world clinical cases, with diverse and complex flow patterns, offer an invaluable resource for developing and testing algorithm robustness and adaptability for real clinical scenarios.
3. High dimensional data with greater acceleration potential: Unlike traditional 2D or 3D image reconstruction tasks, MR 4D Flow introduces a fourth dimension scenario (spatial + temporal dimension), significantly increasing data complexity while offering greater potential for acceleration methods and approaches. This challenge explores the limits of extreme acceleration factors, leveraging the unique properties of 4D flow data to push the

boundary of imaging speed.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

- Addressing barriers to clinical adoption: The challenge directly targets the two major obstacles limiting the clinical use of MR 4D flow: long acquisition times and computationally intensive reconstruction processes. By fostering algorithms that achieve ultra-fast imaging and reconstruction, the challenge paves the way for integrating 4D flow into routine cardiovascular diagnostics, reducing patient burden and improving clinical workflow efficiency.
- Facilitating a wide range of clinical applications: The focus on accurate quantification of hemodynamic parameters under extreme acceleration ensures that reconstructed outputs meet clinical standards. This has direct implications for diagnosing and managing complex cardiovascular diseases such as aortic stenosis, aneurysms, and dissections, etc.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

This challenge will be jointly hosted by the CMRxRecon Committee and the Society for Cardiovascular Magnetic Resonance (SCMR) society. It could potentially be part of the Statistical Atlases and Computational Modeling of the Heart (STACOM) workshop. We have been collaborating with STACOM for three consecutive years.

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

2 Hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

We expect full participation from 50~80 teams at MICCAI 2026. This is estimated from the previous CMRxMotion2022, CMRxRecon2023 and CMRxRecon2024 challenges, in which more than 300 teams registered each challenge and nearly 30 teams completed all stages of the challenge, including the final submission of the Docker container and the conference paper. According to the post-event survey conducted last year, all the participating teams who filled out the questionnaire expressed their willingness to continue participating in the next challenge. We expect a considerable increase of participants this year, due to the fast-growing research communities of CMR, fast imaging, generative AI, and foundation models. This anticipation is also based on the growing popularity of the CMRxRecon2023 dataset (330 downloads, <https://www.synapse.org/#!Synapse:syn51471091/wiki/622170>) and the CMRxRecon2024 dataset (220 downloads, and the number is still growing, <https://www.synapse.org/#!Synapse:syn54951257/wiki/627141>).

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

Individual challenge papers will be published in LNCS proceedings as part of the STACOM workshop. After the challenge, we will summarize the results in a challenge paper and submit it to a high-impact journal (e.g., Nature Medicine, Nature Machine Intelligence, Medical Image Analysis, IEEE Transactions on Medical Imaging, Journal of Cardiovascular Magnetic Resonance).

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

Participants are expected to train models in their local computational environments and to submit docker containers on our Synapse platform (<https://www.synapse.org/#!/Synapse:syn59814210/wiki/628454>). Training and validation data are available for registered teams to download. A leaderboard will be maintained on the Synapse platform during the validation phase. For the fairness of final evaluation, participants are required to submit their docker containers on Synapse platform and we will use the organizers' servers for testing. We will also require the teams to report their computational cost and optionally carbon footprint for model development. Regarding the computer configuration we plan to use for the testing phase, it is as follows:

OS: Linux (RockyOS 9)

CPU: 2.0GHz, 112 cores;

RAM: 64 GB;

GPU: A6000 (48 GB VRAM, single GPU);

GPU Driver Version: 550;

CUDA Version: 12.4;

Time Limitation: 20 hours/team for each task.

For the on-site day, we will take a hybrid form to guarantee the participation of all the teams and audiences. We will reveal the challenge outcome and invite the winning teams to present their methods. In addition, to promote open dialogue and collaboration with clinical communities, device manufacturers, and device regulatory bodies, we have been discussing with SCMR society (Michael Markl and Claudia Prieto, who are also the co-organizer of this challenge) to host a joint workshop and invite representatives from the top teams to present their results and exchange ideas during their annual meeting.

TASK 1: Accurate reconstruction under ultra-high acceleration factors

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

MR 4D flow provides high-resolution spatiotemporal data essential for assessing cardiovascular health, yet its clinical adoption is limited by prolonged acquisition times and computational complexity. High acceleration through k-space undersampling offers a potential solution but poses challenges in maintaining structural integrity and accurate hemodynamic quantification. The challenge aims to develop algorithms capable of rapidly and accurately reconstructing 4D flow images under ultra-high acceleration factors, with a focus on evaluating both hemodynamic parameters and image quality.

Unlike previous CMRxRecon series challenges that primarily addressed multi-parametric 2D and 3D cardiac imaging, this task focuses on the reconstruction of 4D flow, a more complex modality that demands high accuracy in both structural representation and hemodynamic quantification. Participants are tasked with developing algorithms to address the challenges of extreme k-space undersampling, where artifacts, noise, and degraded accuracy in flow velocity measurements often arise. The dataset will include cases with clinically relevant complexities, such as aortic stenosis with turbulent jets, aortic regurgitation with reverse flow, aneurysms with complex flow patterns, coarctation with disturbed flow, and dissections with split true and false lumen flows, ensuring that algorithms are robust enough to handle real-world clinical scenarios. Challenging cases, particularly in the test phase, will assess the ability of algorithms to manage these complex blood flow patterns effectively in clinical contexts.

To support this effort, a dataset comprising 200 individuals with 4D flow imaging, including k-space data acquired at multiple acceleration factors—from 10x to 50x—and fully sampled reference data, will be provided. The aorta was chosen as the target region due to its central role in cardiovascular hemodynamics, its diagnostic relevance across a variety of diseases, and the diverse and complex blood flow patterns it exhibits. Evaluation will center on two key objectives: (1) ensuring high fidelity of reconstructed magnitude images to show fine structure, and (2) achieving precise quantification of hemodynamic parameters within the aortic region. These metrics ensure that reconstructed outputs meet both visual and clinical standards for cardiovascular diagnostics.

By addressing these challenges, the challenge aims to drive innovation in MR 4D flow reconstruction, bridging the gap between research and clinical application. This challenge builds on the legacy of previous CMRxRecon competitions, expanding into a domain with greater technical demands and clinical relevance, ultimately paving the way for broader adoption of 4D flow in routine cardiovascular care.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

4D Flow, high acceleration, image reconstruction, hemodynamic quantification, velocity

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Hao Li

Institute of Science and Technology for Brain-inspired Intelligence, Fudan University, China

Chengyan Wang

Human Phenome Institute, Fudan University, China

Michael Markl

SCMR president, Northwestern Univ Chicago, USA

Claudia Prieto

SCMR 2025 programme chair, Kings College London, UK and Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Santiago, Chile

He Wang, Bingyi Wang, Ruiyu Cao, Xin Guo

Institute of Science and Technology for Brain-inspired Intelligence, Fudan University, China

Chen Qin

Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering and I-X, Imperial College London, UK

Xiaobo Qu, Haoyu Zhang, Mingkai Huang

Pen-Tung Sah Institute of Micro-Nano Science and Technology, Xiamen University, China

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Xiahai Zhuang

School of Data Science, Fudan University, China

Jiayu Zhu, Junpu Hu

Shanghai United Imaging Healthcare Advanced Technology Research Institute Co., Ltd., China

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Ziqiang Xu

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Digital Medical Research Center, School of Basic Medical Sciences, Fudan University, Shanghai, China.

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Hao Li, h_li@fudan.edu.cn

Institute of Science and Technology for Brain-inspired Intelligence, Fudan University, China

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

29th International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Intervention (MICCAI 2026), and the Annual Scientific Sessions of the Society for Cardiovascular Magnetic Resonance (SCMR).

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

synapse.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

Website for CMRxMotion2022:<http://cmr.miccai.cloud/>. Synapse platform for

CMRxMotion2022:<https://www.synapse.org/Synapse:syn32407769/wiki/618247> Website for

CMRxRecon2023:<https://cmrxrecon.github.io>. Synapse platform for

CMRxRecon2023:<https://www.synapse.org/#!/Synapse:syn51471091/wiki/622170> Website for

CMRxRecon2024:<https://cmrxrecon.github.io/2024/Home.html> Synapse platform for CMRxRecon2024:

<https://www.synapse.org/#!/Synapse:syn54951257/wiki/627141> Synapse platform for

CMRxRecon2025:<https://www.synapse.org/#!/Synapse:syn59814210/wiki/> Synapse platform for

CMRxRecon2026:<https://www.synapse.org/Synapse:syn64545434/wiki/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The top 5 winners receive monetary awards. We are in active negotiation with the sponsor about the value (approximately \$2000 in total).

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All submissions will be reported in the leaderboard. Participating teams can opt out of publication of their results in the leaderboard.

Prize-winning methods will be announced publicly as part of a scientific session at the MICCAI annual meeting. In addition, we also plan to collaborate with SCMR to host a joint workshop and invite representatives from the top three teams to present and exchange ideas.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Participating teams with a valid submission can nominate their team members as co-authors for the challenge paper. We reserve the right to exclude teams if they break the challenge rules. Participating teams can publish their own results but after a 3-month embargo period.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker container will be accepted as submission through the Synapse platform. Submission details will be published at the time point of challenge announcement.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participating teams are allowed to make 3 formal submissions per task. Only the last run submission is officially counted to rank challenge results. Before the final submission on the test set, participants can test their docker containers on the validation dataset to avoid submission errors.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

[Apr 1, 2026] website opens for registration, release training and validation images

[Apr 10, 2026] submission system opens for validation

[Aug 1, 2026] submission system opens for testing

[Sept 1, 2026] registration and docker submission deadline

[Oct 8, 2026] release final results during the MICCAI annual meeting

[Jan 31, 2027] challenge summary and invited talk from the winners during the SCMR annual meeting

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

We have received ethics approval from the local ethics committee of School of Basic Medical Sciences, Fudan University granted on 17/11/2021, No. 2021-Y060.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

We will provide the 4D flow evaluation code to participants before the challenge officially begins. This code will enable participants to test their algorithms and understand the evaluation process.

The previous CMRxRecon evaluation code is available at <https://github.com/CmrXRecon/CMRxRecon> as a reference for understanding the structure and expectations of the challenge.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The participating teams are suggested to provide links to their code on our website for reproducibility study. However, it is not a condition of participation.

In the past CMRxRecon challenge, all top ten teams have made their code and method details public, and they have allowed us to consolidate all their information:

<https://github.com/CmrXRecon/CMRxRecon/tree/main/ModelPool>.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

We declare no conflicts of interest. Test images will only be accessible to the challenge organizers.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis, Research, Data reduction

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Reconstruction

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort for this challenge includes patients undergoing MR 4D flow imaging for the assessment of aortic hemodynamics. These patients may present with various aortic conditions that impact blood flow dynamics, including but not limited to aortic stenosis, aortic regurgitation, aortic aneurysm, coarctation of the aorta, and dissection. These diseases are clinically significant as they affect cardiovascular function and may require early diagnosis and intervention. The ultimate goal is to enhance the clinical applicability of MR 4D flow imaging by accelerating the acquisition, thus improving diagnostic efficiency and patient care across a wide spectrum of aortic pathologies.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The proposed challenge will release multi-channel k-space data acquired from 200 clinical cases of aortic 4D flow imaging. The dataset will originate from 2~3 medical centers, ensuring diversity in imaging protocols and device configurations. The imaging data represent real world scenarios, including patients with a range of aortic pathologies such as aortic stenosis, aortic regurgitation, aortic aneurysm, coarctation of the aorta, aortic dissection, and other hemodynamic disorders. Ethical approvals for data acquisition will be obtained from all participating centers.

The dataset will include k-space data acquired on scanners from mainstream vendors (e.g., Siemens, Philips, GE, United Imaging) at field strengths of 1.5T and 3.0T. To simulate real-world clinical conditions, the dataset will feature various blood flow patterns, anatomical complexities, and pathological conditions to challenge and evaluate reconstruction algorithms effectively.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Magnetic Resonance Imaging

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

none

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

none

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary,

differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The data for this challenge originates from MR 4D flow imaging of the aorta, focusing on the thoracic and abdominal regions. The imaging encompasses the ascending aorta, aortic arch, and descending aorta, providing comprehensive spatiotemporal hemodynamic information critical for assessing blood flow patterns, vascular health, and related cardiovascular conditions.

The target cohort represents patients requiring advanced aortic hemodynamic assessment in clinical practice, including those with conditions such as aortic aneurysms, coarctation, dissections, and valve-related abnormalities. The challenge cohort consists of 200 cases of aortic MR 4D flow data collected from 2~3 clinical centers. This dataset captures a diverse range of anatomical structures, blood flow patterns, and clinical scenarios, ensuring robust training and evaluation conditions for the algorithms developed by participants.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm target is to reconstruct highly undersampled MR 4D flow k-space data from the aorta, focusing on accurate quantification of hemodynamic parameters, such as blood flow velocity and flow rate, while also maintaining high-quality magnitude images. Reliable velocity field reconstruction is essential for evaluating cardiovascular health and blood flow patterns, providing the clinical insights necessary for informed decision-making.

Acceleration is a key aspect of this task, as it directly addresses the prolonged acquisition times that currently hinder the clinical adoption of 4D flow. By enabling higher undersampling rates, algorithms can significantly reduce scan durations, moving closer to the clinically desired range of under 5 minutes, while still maintaining diagnostic accuracy. Achieving this balance is vital for improving patient comfort, increasing scanner throughput, and broadening the accessibility of this technology in routine practice.

Participants' algorithms are designed to tackle the challenges of highly accelerated undersampling, ensuring precise velocity quantification alongside adequate structural fidelity in magnitude images, all within clinically feasible acquisition and reconstruction times. The task aims to achieve reconstructions that meet clinical standards for both quantitative hemodynamic analysis and visual representation, ultimately facilitating the broader adoption of 4D flow in cardiovascular diagnostics.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy, Consistency

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The data for this challenge is acquired using 1.5T or 3T MRI scanners from leading manufacturers at 2~3 clinical centers. All scans utilize advanced multi-channel receive coils optimized for thoracic and abdominal imaging, ensuring high-quality data acquisition for MR 4D flow imaging.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

The imaging protocols are based on established standards for MR 4D flow studies, tailored for aortic flow assessment. Specific parameters include:

Field of View (FOV): Approximately $270 \times 270 \times 60\text{-}90$ mm³, covering the ascending aorta to the abdominal aorta.

Spatial Resolution: 2-3 mm isotropic voxels.

Temporal Resolution: Ranges from 29 to 35 ms across cardiac phases, depending on physiological conditions.

Velocity Encoding (VENC): Set to 150-300 cm/s for accurate measurement of blood flow velocities.

Sequence Type: Retrospective ECG-gated 4D flow MRI using GRAPPA (R=2), with fully sampled datasets reconstructed using the standard GRAPPA algorithm.

The acquisition process adheres to consensus recommendations for 4D flow studies, incorporating robust respiratory control mechanisms, such as navigator acceptance windows ($\pm 7\text{-}8$ mm), to minimize motion artifacts.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

The following centers have already contacted us and can support our data collection. Additionally, we are actively reaching out to more international medical centers in the hope of collecting raw data from more sources.

Zhangjiang Imaging Center, Fudan University, China

Department of Radiology, Zhongshan Hospital, Fudan University, China

Department of Radiology, Ren Ji Hospital, School of Medicine, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, Shanghai, China

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Data are acquired with a team of radiographers and clinical advisors as appropriate.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

A case in this challenge refers to the complete dataset from a single MR 4D flow imaging session of the aorta, containing all inputs required for the reconstruction task and corresponding reference outputs for evaluation. Each case includes undersampled k-space data acquired with acceleration factors of 10, 20, 30, 40, and 50, as well as fully sampled k-space data reconstructed into magnitude images and velocity fields to serve as ground truth. The reconstruction outputs, including magnitude images and velocity fields, are critical for assessing both visual fidelity and hemodynamic accuracy.

Training cases will include fully sampled k-space data reconstructed using the standard GRAPPA algorithm, along with undersampling patterns and manual aortic segmentations. These datasets, provided in .mat format, will also include metadata such as velocity encoding (VENC) and resolution details. Validation and test cases will contain undersampled k-space data and manual segmentations, but fully sampled reference data will be retained by the organizers for evaluation.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The dataset for this challenge includes a total of 200 cases of aortic MR 4D flow data. Specifically:

Training cases: 130 fully sampled cases.

Validation cases: 30 undersampled cases with varying acceleration factors, along with their fully sampled reference data.

Test cases: 40 undersampled cases with varying acceleration factors, including data from an additional external validation center not present in the training or validation sets. This external test data ensures the evaluation of algorithm generalizability to unseen clinical scenarios. The fully sampled reference data for test cases will remain hidden until the challenge concludes.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

The dataset includes 130 training cases, 30 validation cases, and 40 test cases, ensuring a balanced approach to model development and evaluation. The training set (70% of the data) provides sufficient diversity for robust algorithm training, while the validation and test sets (15% each) allow for fine-tuning and unbiased performance assessment. The case proportions are based on prior successful CMRxRecon challenges, ensuring effective training and rigorous evaluation.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

This dataset will include a diverse range of disease types, and age distributions. We will aim for an age and gender balance between the training and test data.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

40 undersampled cases with varying acceleration factors, including data from an additional external validation center not present in the training or validation sets. This external test data ensures the evaluation of algorithm generalizability to unseen clinical scenarios. The fully sampled reference data for test cases will remain hidden until the challenge concludes.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

The reference annotations focus on the aortic region, manually segmented by a single experienced radiologist using MRA (Magnetic Resonance Angiography) images derived from the 4D flow datasets.

Training cases: Manually segmented aorta regions based on MRA images from fully sampled 4D flow data are included for algorithm training.

Validation cases: Segmentations follow the same process as training cases and are provided to participants.

Test cases: Segmentations based on test data MRA images are retained by the organizers for evaluation and not disclosed to participants.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

The annotator received detailed training on segmentation protocols and software tools, including consistent use of manual contouring techniques on MRA images. The guidelines emphasized accurate delineation of the aorta, covering the ascending aorta, arch, and descending segments.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Annotations were performed by a single radiologist with over 10 years of clinical experience in cardiovascular imaging.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Not applicable, as all annotations were performed by a single annotator.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The raw k-space data exported from the scanner will be processed and transformed to '.mat' format using the script provided by our vendor. A readme file will be provided to describe the content and usage of the data.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

N.A.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N.A.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

The assessment methodology in this challenge is based on the work by Vishnevskiy et al. (2020), focusing on both image quality and hemodynamic accuracy. The evaluation is performed exclusively within the segmented aortic region, ensuring clinical relevance. To achieve this, manual aorta segmentations will be provided, and all evaluations will focus on the segmented aortic region to ensure clinical relevance. The following metrics are used:

1. Magnitude Image Quality

To assess the fidelity and structural integrity of reconstructed magnitude images:

Normalized Root Mean Square Error (nRMSE): This metric quantifies the difference in magnitude distribution between reconstructed images (a) and fully sampled reference images (a^{*}).

$$nRMSE(a, a^*) = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (a_i - a_i^*)^2}{N \max(a^*)^2} \right)}$$

a_i: Magnitude value at voxel i in the reconstructed image, a_i^{*}: Magnitude value at voxel i in the fully sampled reference image, N: Total number of voxels in the segmented aortic region.

Structural Similarity Index Measure (SSIM): This metric evaluates the perceptual similarity and structural consistency between reconstructed and reference magnitude images.

2. Flow Velocity Field Accuracy

To evaluate the accuracy of reconstructed velocity fields:

Relative Error (RelErr): This metric measures the relative discrepancy in velocity magnitudes (u) between the reconstructed data (u) and the reference data (u^{*}).

$$RelErr(u, u^*) = \frac{\|u - u^*\|_2}{\|u^*\|_2}$$

$\| \cdot \|_2$: L2 norm of the velocity magnitude.

Angular Error (AngErr): This metric evaluates the angular agreement between the reconstructed (u) and reference velocity vectors (u^{*}).

$$AngErr(u, u^*) = \arccos\left(\frac{u \cdot u^*}{\|u\|_2 \|u^*\|_2}\right)$$

u · u^{*}: Dot product of the velocity vectors.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The selected metrics were chosen to comprehensively assess both magnitude image quality and flow velocity accuracy. These metrics ensure the evaluation of reconstructed images aligns with the dual goals of preserving structural integrity and providing accurate hemodynamic measurements. Following the methodology outlined in Vishnevskiy et al. (2020), these metrics are recognized and validated in the field, ensuring consistency with prior studies and clinical relevance.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

The final ranking of all submitted algorithms is based on their overall performance across all test cases, as follows:

1. Individual Metric Ranking: Each metric (nRMSE, SSIM, RelErr, and AngErr) is evaluated independently by calculating its average value across all test cases. For ranking, lower values are preferred for nRMSE, RelErr, and

AngErr, while higher values are preferred for SSIM.

2. Overall Ranking: The individual rankings across all four metrics are summed to produce a composite score for each algorithm. Algorithms with the lowest composite scores are ranked the highest, reflecting balanced performance in both magnitude image quality and velocity accuracy. We rank algorithms for each metric separately and sum the ranks, so differences in metric scales do not affect the overall evaluation.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Participating teams are required to submit docker containers and process all the cases in the test set on our server. For the cases without valid output, we will assign it to the lowest value of metric.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The composite ranking method comprehensively evaluates algorithms across multiple dimensions, ensuring rankings reflect overall performance rather than focusing on a single metric. The clinical value of MR 4D flow includes both the visual quality of magnitude images and the accuracy of hemodynamic parameters. By assessing magnitude image quality (nRMSE and SSIM) and velocity accuracy (RelErr and AngErr) independently, the ranking method captures all key performance aspects. By summing individual rankings, this method balances the influence of each metric, ensuring fairness and clinical relevance.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

The statistical methods employed in this challenge are designed to ensure robust, unbiased evaluation and ranking of the submitted algorithms. The specific considerations are as follows:

1. Handling Missing Data: No missing data is expected in this challenge, as all test cases are thoroughly verified for completeness before release. Should any missing data arise due to unforeseen circumstances, those specific cases will be excluded from the evaluation to maintain consistency and fairness.
2. Assessment of Variability in Rankings: Variability in rankings is assessed by analyzing the consistency of algorithm performance across all test cases. For each metric, standard deviation and interquartile ranges of individual rankings will be calculated to evaluate variability. Additionally, Kendall's Tau or Spearman's rank correlation will be used to compare rankings across metrics, ensuring that the overall rankings are robust against minor variations in individual metrics.
3. Assumptions and Validation: The ranking scheme assumes that all test cases are representative of real-world clinical scenarios and that the metrics (nRMSE, SSIM, RelErr, AngErr) are independently meaningful for evaluating algorithm performance. Data distribution and assumptions for each metric are validated using statistical tests (e.g., Shapiro-Wilk test for normality where applicable).
4. Software for Statistical Analysis: Statistical analyses and visualizations are performed using Python (e.g., NumPy, SciPy, and Matplotlib libraries) and MATLAB. These tools provide comprehensive support for handling statistical computations, including correlation analysis and rank aggregation.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

Please see the description of metrics and ranking methods above.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

N/A

TASK 2: Fast and accurate reconstruction with limited computational resources

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

MR 4D flow imaging, which provides high-resolution spatiotemporal hemodynamic information, is a powerful cardiovascular imaging tool. However, its widespread clinical adoption faces significant barriers due to the complexity and duration of the reconstruction process. The temporal dimension inherent in 4D flow, capturing multiple time frames across the cardiac cycle, generates significantly larger data volumes than traditional 2D or 3D structural imaging. This leads to higher computational demands and longer processing times, further limiting its feasibility in routine clinical workflows. To address these challenges, Task 2 focuses on developing reconstruction algorithms that can achieve fast processing under limited computational resources while maintaining clinically acceptable image quality and hemodynamic accuracy.

In this task, FlowVN (Vishnevskiy et al., Nat Mach Intell. 2020)—a state-of-the-art reconstruction algorithm—serves as the benchmark reference. Participants are required to design algorithms that meet or exceed FlowVN's performance in three quality metrics: absolute velocity error (AVE), normalized root mean square error (nRMSE), and structural similarity index (SSIM). The primary evaluation criterion is reconstruction time, measured on a standardized computational environment (a single NVIDIA A6000 GPU with 48 GB VRAM). Only submissions that match or surpass FlowVN's quality thresholds in all three metrics will be considered for ranking, with the shortest reconstruction time determining the winner among eligible submissions.

This task aims to push the boundaries of computational efficiency in MR 4D flow reconstruction while ensuring that clinical reliability is not compromised. By fostering the development of fast, efficient, and high-quality reconstruction algorithms, Task 2 seeks to overcome a critical computational bottleneck in MR 4D flow imaging, paving the way for its integration into routine clinical practice and broader adoption in cardiovascular care.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

4D flow, fast reconstruction, computational efficiency, limited resources, hemodynamic accuracy

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Chengyan Wang

Human Phenome Institute, Fudan University, China

Michael Markl

SCMR president, Northwestern Univ Chicago, USA

Claudia Prieto

SCMR 2025 programme chair, Kings College London, UK and Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile, Santiago, Chile

Hao Li, He Wang, Zhensen Chen, Bingyi Wang

Institute of Science and Technology for Brain-inspired Intelligence, Fudan University, China

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Department of Electrical and Electronic Engineering and I-X, Imperial College London, UK

Xiaobo Qu, Haoyu Zhang, Mingkai Huang

Pen-Tung Sah Institute of Micro-Nano Science and Technology, Xiamen University, China

Guang Yang, Zi Wang, Fanwen Wang

Department of Bioengineering and Imperial-X, Imperial College London, UK

Alistair Young,

Kings College London, UK

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Cheng Ouyang

Department of Engineering Science, University of Oxford, UK

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Lianming Wu

Department of Radiology, Ren Ji Hospital, School of Medicine, Shanghai Jiao Tong University, Shanghai, China

Ziqiang Xu

Shanghai Fuying Medical Technology Co., Ltd., China

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Chengyan Wang

E-mail: wangcy@fudan.edu.cn

Human Phenome Institute, Fudan University, China

Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

29th International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer Assisted Intervention (MICCAI 2026), and the Annual Scientific Sessions of the Society for Cardiovascular Magnetic Resonance (SCMR).

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

synapse.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

Website for CMRxMotion2022:<http://cmr.miccai.cloud/>. Synapse platform for CMRxMotion2022:<https://www.synapse.org/Synapse:syn32407769/wiki/618247> Website for CMRxRecon2023:<https://cmrxrecon.github.io>. Synapse platform for CMRxRecon2023:<https://www.synapse.org/#!/Synapse:syn51471091/wiki/622170> Website for CMRxRecon2024:<https://cmrxrecon.github.io/2024/Home.html> Synapse platform for CMRxRecon2024:<https://www.synapse.org/#!/Synapse:syn54951257/wiki/627141> Synapse platform for CMRxRecon2025:<https://www.synapse.org/#!/Synapse:syn59814210/wiki/> Synapse platform for CMRxRecon2026:<https://www.synapse.org/Synapse:syn64545434/wiki/>

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards and not listed in leaderboard

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

The top 5 winners receive monetary awards. We are in active negotiation with the sponsor about the value (approximately \$2000 in total).

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

All submissions will be reported in the leaderboard. Participating teams can opt out of publication of their results in the leaderboard.

Prize-winning methods will be announced publicly as part of a scientific session at the MICCAI annual meeting. In addition, we also plan to collaborate with SCMR to host a joint workshop and invite representatives from the top three teams to present and exchange ideas.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Participating teams with a valid submission can nominate their team members as co-authors for the challenge paper. We reserve the right to exclude teams if they break the challenge rules. Participating teams can publish their own results but after a 3-month embargo period.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

Docker container will be accepted as submission through the Synapse platform. Submission details will be published at the time point of challenge announcement.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participating teams are allowed to make 3 formal submissions per task. Only the last run submission is officially counted to rank challenge results. Before the final submission on the test set, participants can test their docker containers on the validation dataset to avoid submission errors.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

[Apr 1, 2026] website opens for registration, release training and validation images

[Apr 10, 2026] submission system opens for validation

[Aug 1, 2026] submission system opens for testing

[Sept 1, 2026] registration and docker submission deadline

[Oct 8, 2026] release final results during the MICCAI annual meeting

[Jan 31, 2027] challenge summary and invited talk from the winners during the SCMR annual meeting

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

We have received ethics approval from the local ethics committee of School of Basic Medical Sciences, Fudan University granted on 17/11/2021, No. 2021-Y060.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

We will provide the 4D flow evaluation code to participants before the challenge officially begins. This code will enable participants to test their algorithms and understand the evaluation process.

The previous CMRxRecon evaluation code is available at <https://github.com/CmrXRecon/CMRxRecon> as a reference for understanding the structure and expectations of the challenge.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The participating teams are suggested to provide links to their code on our website for reproducibility study. However, it is not a condition of participation.

In the past CMRxRecon challenge, all top ten teams have made their code and method details public, and they have allowed us to consolidate all their information:

<https://github.com/CmrXRecon/CMRxRecon/tree/main/ModelPool>.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

We declare no conflicts of interest. Test images will only be accessible to the challenge organizers.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education

- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis
- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Diagnosis, Research

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Reconstruction

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort for this challenge includes patients undergoing MR 4D flow imaging for the assessment of aortic hemodynamics. These patients may present with various aortic conditions that impact blood flow dynamics,

including but not limited to aortic stenosis, aortic regurgitation, aortic aneurysm, coarctation of the aorta, and dissection. These diseases are clinically significant as they affect cardiovascular function and may require early diagnosis and intervention.

The ultimate goal is to facilitate the integration of MR 4D flow imaging into routine clinical workflows by addressing computational challenges, enabling faster reconstruction times while maintaining reconstruction accuracy relative to reference standards.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

Same as Task 1.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

Magnetic Resonance Imaging

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

none

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

none

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Same as Task 1.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Similar to Task 1, the algorithm target in Task 2 focuses on reconstructing highly undersampled MR 4D flow k-space data from the aorta. However, Task 2 emphasizes computational efficiency, requiring algorithms to achieve fast reconstruction under limited hardware resources (e.g., a single NVIDIA A6000 GPU) while maintaining clinically acceptable accuracy for velocity fields and magnitude images.

Participants are tasked with designing algorithms that meet or exceed the performance of the benchmark algorithm, FlowVN, in terms of complex difference error (Ecomplex). The primary objective is to minimize reconstruction time while ensuring that the reconstructed outputs meet clinical standards for both quantitative hemodynamic analysis and visual quality. This task challenges participants to optimize for speed without compromising the accuracy or reliability necessary for broader clinical adoption of MR 4D flow imaging.

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Accuracy,Consistency,Runtime

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

Consistent with Task 1, the data for this challenge is acquired using 1.5T or 3T MRI scanners from leading manufacturers, including Siemens, Philips, GE and United Imaging, at 2~3 clinical centers. All scans utilize advanced multi-channel receive coils optimized for thoracic and abdominal imaging, ensuring high-quality data acquisition for MR 4D flow imaging.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

Same as Task 1.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

Same as Task 1.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

Data are acquired with a team of radiographers and clinical advisors as appropriate.

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context

information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

Same as Task 1, but the dataset for Task 2 will include fewer acceleration factors, as extremely high acceleration data will not be provided.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

Same as Task 1, but the dataset for Task 2 will include fewer acceleration factors, as extremely high acceleration data will not be provided.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

Same as Task 1.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

Same as Task 1.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

Same as Task 1.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

Same as Task 1.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Same as Task 1.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Same as Task 1.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

Not applicable, as all annotations were performed by a single annotator.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The raw k-space data exported from the scanner will be processed and transformed to '.mat' format using the script provided by our vendor. A readme file will be provided to describe the content and usage of the data.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter- and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

N.A.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

N.A.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

The core objective of this challenge is to evaluate computational efficiency, provided that reconstruction quality meets the clinical benchmark. Similar to Task 1, manual aorta segmentations will be provided, and all evaluations will focus on the segmented aortic region to ensure clinical relevance. The following metrics are used:

1. Reconstruction Quality

Reconstruction quality is assessed using a unified metric, Complex Difference Error (E_{complex}), that evaluates the accuracy of the reconstructed complex-valued data, capturing both magnitude and phase information:

$$E_{\text{complex}} = \sqrt{\left(\sum_{i=1}^N |z_i - i_{\text{ref}}|^2 \right) / N}$$

Where:

$z_i = a_i e^{j\phi_i}$: Reconstructed complex signal, combining magnitude (a_i) and phase (ϕ_i).

i_{ref} : Fully sampled reference complex signal.

N : Total number of voxels in the manually segmented aortic region.

Submissions must achieve an E_{complex} value equivalent to or better than FlowVN—the benchmark algorithm—to qualify for ranking.

2. Computational Efficiency

After meeting the reconstruction quality threshold, algorithms are ranked based on their computational efficiency. Reconstruction time per case, measured in seconds, is evaluated on a standardized computational platform (a single NVIDIA A6000 GPU with 48 GB VRAM). Algorithms with shorter reconstruction times will achieve higher rankings.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

The selected metrics were chosen to comprehensively assess both magnitude image quality and flow velocity accuracy. These metrics ensure the evaluation of reconstructed images aligns with the dual goals of preserving structural integrity and providing accurate hemodynamic measurements. Following the methodology outlined in

Vishnevskiy et al. (2020), these metrics are recognized and validated in the field, ensuring consistency with prior studies and clinical relevance.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

The ranking for this challenge focuses on computational efficiency while ensuring reconstruction quality meets the clinical benchmark. The process is as follows:

Reconstruction Quality Threshold: Submissions are first evaluated for reconstruction quality using the Complex Difference Error (E_{complex}), which captures both magnitude and phase accuracy. Only algorithms achieving an E_{complex} value equivalent to or better than the benchmark algorithm, FlowVN, qualify for ranking.

Final Ranking Based on Computational Efficiency: Among submissions meeting the reconstruction quality threshold, algorithms are ranked based on their reconstruction time, measured in seconds on a standardized computational platform (a single NVIDIA A6000 GPU with 48 GB VRAM). Shorter reconstruction times result in higher rankings, reflecting the challenge's primary focus on efficiency.

This ranking scheme ensures that submissions are clinically reliable while driving advancements in computational efficiency.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Participating teams are required to submit docker containers and process all the cases in the test set on our server. For the cases without valid output, we will assign it to the lowest value of metric.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

The described ranking scheme ensures a balance between computational efficiency and reconstruction quality, the core objectives of Task 2. By requiring submissions to meet or exceed the FlowVN benchmark for quality, the challenge ensures that speed improvements are not achieved at the expense of clinical relevance. Algorithms that pass the quality threshold are then ranked based on reconstruction time, emphasizing efficiency as the primary criterion.

Using the Complex Difference Error (E_{complex}) simplifies the evaluation process compared to the multiple metrics used in Task 1. By integrating magnitude and phase accuracy into a single metric, E_{complex} reduces complexity while maintaining a comprehensive assessment of reconstruction quality. This unified approach provides a clear and actionable benchmark, making evaluation straightforward and helping participants align their efforts with challenge goals.

This scheme reflects clinical priorities for rapid and reliable MR 4D Flow reconstruction under computational constraints. A standardized computational platform ensures fairness and comparability, supporting the development of algorithms that are both efficient and robust, fostering innovations suitable for clinical application.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,

- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

The statistical methods employed in this challenge align with those used in Task 1, ensuring consistency across evaluations.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

Please see the description of metrics and ranking methods above.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

N/A

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

Reference of the CMR imaging acquisition protocol:

1. Wang C, Lyu J, Wang S, et al. CMRxRecon: A publicly available k-space dataset and benchmark to advance deep learning for cardiac MRI. *Scientific Data*, 2024, 11(1): 687.
2. Wang C, Lyu J, Wang S, et al. CMRxRecon: An open cardiac MRI dataset for the competition of accelerated image reconstruction. *arXiv preprint arXiv:2309.10836*, 2023.
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Reference for previously developed reconstruction algorithms:

1. Wang C, Jang J, Neisius U, et al. Black blood myocardial T2 mapping. *Magnetic resonance in medicine*. 2019, 81(1): 153-166.
2. Lyu J, Wang S, Tian Y, Zou J, Dong S, Wang C, Aviles-Rivero AI, Qin J. STADNet: Spatial-Temporal Attention-Guided Dual-Path Network for cardiac cine MRI super-resolution. *Medical Image Analysis*, 2024;94:103142.

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4. Lyu J, Tian Y, Cai Q, Wang C*, Qin J. Adaptive channel-modulated personalized federated learning for magnetic resonance image reconstruction. *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, 2023, 165: 107330.
5. Qin C, Schlemper J, Caballero J, et al. Convolutional recurrent neural networks for dynamic MR image reconstruction. *IEEE transactions on medical imaging*, 2018, 38(1): 280-290.
6. Qin C, Duan J, Hammernik K, et al. Complementary time-frequency domain networks for dynamic parallel MR image reconstruction. *Magnetic Resonance in Medicine*, 2021, 86(6): 3274-3291.
7. Lyu J, Tian Y, Cai Q, et al. Adaptive channel-modulated personalized federated learning for magnetic resonance image reconstruction. *Computers in Biology and Medicine*, 2023, 165: 107330.
8. Lyu J, Tong X, Wang C. Parallel Imaging With a Combination of SENSE and Generative Adversarial Networks (GAN). *Quantitative Imaging in Medicine and Surgery*. 2020, 10(12): 2260-2273.
9. Lyu J, Sui B, Wang C, et al. DuDoCAF: Dual-Domain Cross-Attention Fusion with Recurrent Transformer for Fast Multi-contrast MR Imaging. *International Conference on Medical Image Computing and Computer-Assisted Intervention*. Springer, Cham, 2022: 474-484.
10. Ouyang C, Schlemper K, et al. Generalizing Deep Learning MRI Reconstruction across Different Domains, arXiv preprint arXiv: 1902.10815, 2019.

Other references:

1. Bissell MM, Raimondi F, Ait Ali L, Allen BD, Barker AJ, Bolger A, et al. 4D Flow cardiovascular magnetic resonance consensus statement: 2023 update. *JOURNAL OF CARDIOVASCULAR MAGNETIC RESONANCE*. 2023;25.
2. Pathrose A, Ma L, Berhane H, Scott MB, Chow K, Forman C, et al. Highly accelerated aortic 4D flow MRI using compressed sensing: Performance at different acceleration factors in patients with aortic disease. *MAGNETIC RESONANCE IN MEDICINE*. 2021;85:2174-87.
3. Ma LE, Markl M, Chow K, Huh H, Forman C, Vali A, et al. Aortic 4D flow MRI in 2 minutes using compressed sensing, respiratory controlled adaptive k-space reordering, and inline reconstruction. *MAGNETIC RESONANCE IN MEDICINE*. 2019;81:3675-90.
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Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

We hope to hold this challenge in 2026, as we need more than six months to collect high-quality raw data for 4D flow. Therefore, we would like to obtain approval from the organizing committee in advance.